

LOW-ENERGY IMPACT TESTING ON EPOXY COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH DNA-FUNCTIONALIZED CARBON NANOTUBES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we present experimental results of the impact resistance of epoxy composite structures reinforced with DNA-functionalized carbon nanotubes following low energy impact tests. Izod tests were conducted according to ASTM standards on different specimens. In particular, we tested three types of specimens for comparison: neat resin, epoxy composites reinforced with pristine carbon nanotubes, and epoxy composites reinforced with DNA-functionalized carbon nanotubes. The nanocomposites were realized at fixed percentage of nanofillers equal to 0.5 % by weight. The fracture surfaces of the three types of nanocomposites after the Izod test were visually investigated under an optical microscope. Dropped weight tests were conducted on composite plates fabricated with the above mentioned materials, in order to simulate low velocity impact conditions with energy of 9.8 J.

1 INTRODUCTION

The discovery of the exceptional electrical, thermal and mechanical properties of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) has initiated many investigations into the possibility to embed them in polymer matrices with the main objective of creating advanced multifunctional structures [1-4]. This opportunity is particularly relevant in the aerospace field, where the use of such composite materials can satisfy the lightweight requirement by replacing complex and heavier subsystems of a spacecraft. For these reasons, CNTs are largely investigated as reinforcements for the epoxy matrix, which is the predominant polymer used for structural applications in spacecraft and aircraft vehicles.

Despite the high elastic modulus and tensile strength of CNTs, the enhancing of the mechanical properties of epoxy resins reinforced by CNTs, either single-walled or multi-walled, are largely unpredictable due to their strong dependence on the manufacturing process [5-10]. In particular, the mechanical performance of epoxy nanocomposites is greatly affected by the dispersion efficiency of the nanotubes inside the polymer matrix. To improve their dispersion in epoxy resins, CNTs are commonly functionalized following covalent strategies [5]. Chemical treatments, by which functional groups are attached to the nanotube walls, make the CNTs more compatible with the polymer matrix, thus improving the homogeneity of the dispersion. However, surface modifications cause a degradation of the overall CNTs properties, so that the benefits added by the more homogenous dispersion are in fact lost in the final composite material.

In previous works, we have demonstrated the possibility to obtain a homogeneous dispersion of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) in an epoxy resin using a non-covalent functionalization based on DNA wrapping [11, 12]. The advantage of this approach is that MWCNTs maintain the intact features of pristine nanotubes. The aim of this study is to investigate the effects of the use of such functionalization on the impact resistance of the epoxy composite material. In addition, we investigate the low-energy impact behavior using a dropped weight test, in order to assess on a whole the impact resistance of such materials. For these tests we used an experimental set-up consisting of an in-house drop tower system capable to simulate low velocity impact conditions with energy of 9.8 J. The performance evaluation of the different composite materials is completed by linking sample behavior during the impact test to microscopy inspection of the fracture surfaces.

2 MATERIALS AND PROCESSING

The multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) used in this study were the industrial grade NC7000 purchased from Nanocyl SA (Belgium), with outer diameter of 9.5-10 nm and an average length of 1.5 μm . High-purity double-stranded DNA ($A_{260}/A_{280} = 1.82$, protein content $< 0.1\%$) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received. The epoxy matrix selected for this study was the two-component PRIME 20LV resin with slow hardener manufactured by Gurit Ltd (UK).

The procedure for the non-covalent functionalization of multi-walled CNTs by DNA was previously reported [11-13]. Briefly, the procedure consisted in sonicating the MWCNTs in a DNA aqueous solution (1 mg/mL) for 60 min in a cold bath to avoid DNA denaturation [12]. The blend ratio between MWCNTs and DNA was 1:1 (by weight) since this proportion guarantees a stable dispersion of CNT/DNA complexes in water for days. With the sonication procedure, DNA molecules wrap around the nanotubes structure due to π - π stacking of the DNA bases on the aromatic carbon rings, whereas the negatively-charged phosphate groups on the DNA molecule are exposed to water and allow for the homogeneous dispersion of the CNTs in solution [13]. The efficiency of the DNA-mediated dispersion was demonstrated to be independent of the length of the DNA molecules, considering that the duration of the sonication process might shorten the DNA strands. DNA-wrapped MWCNTs aqueous solutions were filtered and then dried in oven at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for several hours to remove any humidity residues.

DNA-wrapped MWCNTs and pristine MWCNTs were dispersed at 0.5 wt. % in the epoxy matrix following the same two-step procedure: mechanical stirring for about 10 minutes and sonication for about 1 h. After that, nanocomposites were fabricated by adding the hardener at 30% in volume with respect to the matrix content. The mixture was degassed to ensure elimination of air bubbles formed during the stirring step. The specimens were fabricated by pouring the mixture in a metal mold, and curing it in oven at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 16 h.

3 TEST METHODS

With the aim to check the effect of the DNA non-covalent functionalization on the mechanical properties of the MWCNT-based composite, we compared results of specimens fabricated with neat resin and two types of fillers, pristine MWCNTs and DNA-functionalized MWCNTs, both at 0.5 wt. % of inclusion within the selected polymeric matrix.

Izod tests were performed with the pendulum PSW 750 (Zwick GmbH & Co.KG) according to ASTM Standard 256-04 [14]. Samples were prepared by casting the mixture into rectangular shaped cavities for standard notched (1 mm) specimens. Six samples for each composite formulation were tested.

Figure 1: Dimensions of the specimens for the Izod test.

The impact strength (IS) was calculated as follows:

$$IS = \Delta E / w(t - a) \quad (1)$$

where ΔE is the impact energy [kJ], w is the specimen width [m], t is the specimen thickness [m], a is the notch length [m].

The experimental set-up to test the composite plates consists of an in-house built drop tower system, where low-velocity impact conditions can be simulated (Fig. 2). The performance evaluation of the impact behavior is first linked to the observation of the samples during the test, followed by the visual inspection of the fragments and analysis of the fracture surfaces under an optical microscope. It should be noted that such characterization is far from been exhaustive, and the main purpose of this study is to compare qualitatively the effect of the DNA-MWCNT reinforcement in the epoxy resin system with respect to pristine MWCNT. However, thanks to a high degree of test reproducibility, the adopted testing set-up allowed to achieve a direct validation of both the current research direction and the samples manufacturing process.

Figure 2: Schematic of the impact test set-up.

Square tile samples with size of 250 mm x 250 mm were fabricated with thickness of 4 mm. The drop tower system was an aluminum structure with a 1.90 m-high hollow pipe that can be hooked at adjustable heights to a shorter column fixed on the apparatus platform. On the top of the pipe a 0.5-kg sharpened weight is inserted into the hollow pipe (diameter ~ 42 mm), so that it may impact by gravity free-fall on the tile square sample clamped at the bottom. Lateral bungee cords were used to avoid vertical displacements (rebounds) of the tile at the impact. The inner pipe diameter acted as a guide to the vertical motion of the weight. Greasing operations of both the weight and the pipe inner wall were necessary to minimize the friction effects as much as possible.

The pipe is positioned at a level so that there is no contact with the weight during the impact, so to avoid alterations of the bullet-target interaction dynamics. At such conditions, the impact kinetic energy $E_c = mg\Delta h$ may be evaluated around 9.8 J, and the corresponding velocity $v = (2mg\Delta h)^{1/2}$ is 6.2 m/s.

4 RESULTS

Izod test

Table 1 summarizes the average values with corresponding standard deviations of the impact strength for the three types of materials. The average impact strength of the pristine MWCNT/epoxy composites is about 12% increased with respect to the impact strength of the neat epoxy. These results are in line with those available in the literature [15, 16]. A significant difference can be noted in the values of the standard deviations among the different samples. Izod tests were highly reproducible for the neat resin, whereas the pristine MWCNT/epoxy composites present a larger scattering of the data. This phenomenon is due to the fact that pristine MWCNTs are difficult to disperse in the polymer matrix. In fact, they form large entanglements that act as point of defects inside the composite instead

of reinforcing it. As a consequence, the spatial distribution of both entangled MWCNTs and disentangled MWCNTs, which can be located in the bulk, at the surface, near the surface, or at an edge, may facilitate crack initiation and propagation. Hence, the impact strength may be dramatically different from specimen to specimen. For these samples, test reproducibility depends on the quality of the dispersion, meaning the capacity to create a disentangled MWCNTs network inside the matrix. In this way, the data scattering will be strongly reduced.

Material	Impact strength [kJ/m ²]	Standard deviation [kJ/m ²]
Neat PRIME 20LV	1.74	0.05
MWCNT/PRIME 20LV	1.95	0.45
DNA-MWCNT/PRIME 20LV	1.43	0.14

Table 1: Impact strengths by Izod test of neat epoxy resin PRIME 20LV, pristine MWCNTs/epoxy composites (0.5/100 by weight) and DNA-MWCNTs/epoxy composites (0.5/100 by weight).

For the case of DNA-functionalized MWCNT/epoxy composites the standard deviation shows a very low value indicating a good reproducibility of the test data. This result means that the DNA-functionalized MWCNTs are well dispersed inside the epoxy matrix. On the other hand, at first analysis, the DNA functionalization seems to decrease the mechanical properties of the composite from an absorbed energy point of view. In fact, the impact strength of the DNA-MWCNT/epoxy composites is lower of about 18% with respect to the case of the neat resin. Further investigations showed that such results can be related to the different polymerization grade reached by the specimens during the cure step. In fact, a preliminary isothermal analysis conducted by differential scanning calorimeter at 50 °C revealed that the DNA-MWCNTs/epoxy composites require the double time of the neat resin to reach the peak of the reticulation. Therefore, the DNA-MWCNTs /epoxy specimens tested here were characterized by a lower grade of polymerization with respect to the neat resin, considering that all specimens had the same thermal history. The pristine MWCNTs also showed a certain delay in the polymerization, but the peak of polymerization is near the point of the neat resin.

Material	Peak time [min]
Neat PRIME 20LV	27
MWCNT/PRIME 20LV	38
DNA-MWCNT/PRIME 20LV	62

Table 2: Peak time of polymerization for neat epoxy, pristine MWCNTs/epoxy mixture (0.5/100 by weight) and DNA-MWCNTs/epoxy mixture (0.5/100 by weight) by isothermal analysis at curing temperature of 50 °C.

Fig. 3 shows optical images of the typical fracture surfaces for the three types of materials after impact. The neat epoxy (Fig. 3a) shows the distinctive smooth surface of the glassy polymer with radial striations on the fracture surface. The striations converge versus the zone of the crack initiation site, i.e. the area of the impact hammer. Similar features are visible in the fractured surface of pristine MWCNTs/epoxy composites. It can be observed that the embedded DNA-functionalized MWCNTs significantly modified the morphology of the fracture surface. The fracture surface appeared to have a large degree of roughness. This rough fracture surface can be explained by the crack deflection and the continual crack propagation occurring on two slightly different fracture planes. This would be due to the presence of large quantity of nanotubes. The tips were forced to frequently change their propagation direction. As a result, tough fracture morphology with a great deal of short and highly curved patterns of the crack propagation was revealed. The fracture surface also showed the nanotube

dispersion in the epoxy resin. The nanotubes were well dispersed in the nanocomposites, not forming aggregates.

Figure 3: Optical micrographs of the fracture surface of the composite samples after Izod test. (a) neat epoxy, (b) pristine-MWCNTs/epoxy composites (0.5/100 by weight) and (c) DNA-MWCNTs/epoxy composites (0.5/100 by weight).

Low impact test

Further investigations in the low impact range were conducted on carbon filler-reinforced epoxy materials by means of a dropped weight test, with the aim to assess the impact resistance properties of such composite materials on a whole. Three types of tile samples were tested: neat resin as non-reinforced reference samples with thickness of 3.9 ± 0.5 mm, pristine MWCNT/epoxy nanocomposites with 3.7 ± 0.5 mm, and DNA-MWCNT/epoxy nanocomposites with thickness of 3.9 ± 0.4 mm.

In Fig. 4 the responses of the different materials under testing are illustrated. None of the samples withstood the impact. All were broken in several fragments, but the breaking route was different for the different materials. In particular, the MWCNT-reinforced materials broke in a number of pieces noticeably less than what occurred for the neat resin samples, which were disintegrated by the knock, thus highlighting an effective improvement by the powder fillers in terms of energy absorption. The most striking result was discovered in the tiles fabricated from DNA-functionalized MWCNTs/epoxy composite. These were split in two parts only, with the fractures originating quite far from the impact point, where, in addition, no macroscopic trace of the hit was discovered. Such an intriguing response gives evidence of a real efficient behavior of the epoxy composite reinforced with DNA-modified carbon nanotubes, as the energy absorption capability is widely increased by the matrix-filler load transfer optimization.

This feature is even more evident by the short videos recorded during the tests: unlike the other cases, the heavy bullet does not perforate the optimized tile but bounces on it, thus inducing visible flexure vibrations to the slab till the breaking point, likely due to a non-completely homogenous sample, is reached. Such mechanical behavior is in agreement with the well-known elastic properties of MWCNTs, which are capable to withstand tensional, torsional, buckling and compression stresses that are unsustainable by common materials. On the other hand, the need of a suitable chemical treatment of the MWCNTs before their utilization inside a polymeric matrix has to be underlined, since pristine MWCNT-reinforced materials show a behavior that is not significantly better than what is obtained with DNA-functionalized MWCNT-reinforced composites. This behavior is clearly due to the strong entanglement of pure MWCNTs, which gives rise to large agglomerates (even of micrometric dimensions) thus preventing a correct dispersion of the filler inside the polymer matrix.

Figure 4: View of tiles after dropped weight test. (a) neat epoxy, (b) pristine-MWCNTs/epoxy composites (0.5/100 by weight) and (c) DNA-MWCNTs/epoxy composites (0.5/100 by weight). Size of the tile samples is 250 mm x 250 mm.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The effects of the addition of DNA-functionalized MWCNTs to epoxy matrices with respect to the material impact properties were investigated under different levels of impact energy. Commercial MWCNTs were sonicated in solutions of double-stranded DNA to achieve a non-covalent functionalization that would enhance the dispersion of the carbon nanotubes inside the polymer matrix (PRIME 20LV).

The experimental results point to the necessity to extend the curing time or to increase the curing temperature in order to guarantee a proper grade of curing of the epoxy composites containing DNA-functionalized MWCNTs. The resilience investigation shows a high grade of dispersion of the carbon nanotubes with the non-covalent DNA functionalization.

Dropped weight tests were carried out in order to assess the impact resistance properties in the low-energy range of the composites reinforced by the functionalized MWCNTs at 0.5 wt. %. These performances were compared to those provided by the composite materials reinforced by analogous weight percentages of pristine MWCNTs powder, in order to assess the effectiveness of the nano-filler itself and after the non-covalent functionalization treatment.

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REFERENCES

- [1] L. S. Schadler, S. C. Giannaris and P. M. Ajayan, Load transfer in carbon nanotube epoxy composites, *Applied Physics Letters*, **73**, 1998, pp. 3842-3844 (doi: [10.1063/1.122911](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.122911)).
- [2] Y. J. Kim, T. S. Shin, H. D. Choi, J. H. Kwon, Y.-C. Chung and H. G. Yoon, Electrical conductivity of chemically modified multiwalled carbon nanotube/epoxy composites, *Carbon*, **43**, 2005, pp. 23-30 (doi: [10.1016/j.carbon.2004.08.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2004.08.015)).
- [3] D. Micheli, C. Apollo, R. Pastore, R. Bueno Morles, S. Laurenzi and M. Marchetti, Nanostructured composite materials for electromagnetic interference shielding applications, *Acta Astronautica*, **69**, 2011, pp. 747-757 (doi: [10.1016/j.actaastro.2011.06.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2011.06.004)).
- [4] B. Yakobson and P. Avouris, Mechanical properties of carbon nanotubes, *Carbon nanotubes: synthesis, structure, properties, and applications* (Eds. M. Dresselhaus, G. Dresselhaus, P. Avouris), Springer, New York, 2001, pp. 287-328.
- [5] L. Ci and J. Bai, The reinforcement role of carbon nanotubes in epoxy composites with different matrix stiffness, *Composites Science and Technology*, **66**, 2006, pp. 599-603 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2005.05.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2005.05.020)).

- [6] P.-C. Ma, N. A. Siddiqui, G. Marom and J.-K. Kim, Dispersion and functionalization of carbon nanotubes for polymer-based nanocomposites: A review, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **41**, 2010, pp.1345-1367 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2010.07.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2010.07.003)).
- [7] J. Kathi, K.-Y. Rhee and J. H. Lee, Effect of chemical functionalization of multi-walled carbon nanotubes with 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane on mechanical and morphological properties of epoxy nanocomposites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **40**, 2009, pp. 800-809 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2009.04.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2009.04.001)).
- [8] P.-C. Ma, S.-Y. Mo, B.-Z. Tang and J.-K. Kim, Dispersion, interfacial interaction and re-agglomeration of functionalized carbon nanotubes in epoxy composites, *Carbon*, **48**, 2010, pp. 1824-1834 (doi: [10.1016/j.carbon.2010.01.028](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2010.01.028)).
- [9] Y.-H. Liao, O. Marietta-Tondin, Z. Liang, C. Zhang and B. Wang, Investigation of the dispersion process of SWNTs/SC-15 epoxy resin nanocomposites, *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, **385**, 2004, pp. 175-181 (doi: [10.1016/j.msea.2004.06.031](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2004.06.031)).
- [10] K.-T. Lau, C. Gu, and D. Hui, A critical review on nanotube and nanotube/nanoclay related polymer composite materials, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **37**, 2006, pp. 425-436 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesb.2006.02.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2006.02.020)).
- [11] M. G. Santonicola, S. Laurenzi and M. Marchetti, DNA-based sensors integrated in composite polymeric materials for monitoring radiation damage in space environment, *Proceedings of 61st International Astronautical Congress, IAC 2010, Prague, Czech Republic, September 27-October 1, 2010*, Paper 85176, **13**, 2010, pp. 10938-10940.
- [12] S. Laurenzi, M. Sirilli, M. Pinna and M. G. Santonicola, DNA-assisted dispersion of multi-walled CNTs in epoxy polymer matrix, *Materials Research Society Symposium Proceedings Spring 2014 - Symposium MM-Nanotubes and related nanostructures (Eds. D. Futaba, Y. K. Yap), San Francisco, USA, April 21-25, 2014*, Cambridge University Press, **1700**, 2014, pp. 103-108 (doi: [10.1557/opl.2014.573](https://doi.org/10.1557/opl.2014.573)).
- [13] M. G. Santonicola, S. Laurenzi and P. M. Schön, Self-assembled carbon nanotube-DNA hybrids at the nanoscale: morphological and conductive properties probed by atomic force microscopy, *Materials Research Society Symposium Proceedings Spring 2014 - Symposium MM-Nanotubes and related nanostructures, 2014 (Eds. D. Futaba, Y. K. Yap), San Francisco, USA, April 21-25, 2014*, Cambridge University Press, **1700**, 2014, pp 47-52 (doi: [10.1557/opl.2014.552](https://doi.org/10.1557/opl.2014.552)).
- [14] American Society for Testing Materials, Standard Test Methods for Determining the Izod Impact Resistance of Plastics, ASTM, 256-04, 2004.
- [15] S. Laurenzi, R. Pastore, G. Giannini and M. Marchetti, Experimental study of impact resistance in multi-walled carbon nanotube reinforced epoxy, *Composite Structures*, **99**, 2013, pp. 62-68 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2012.12.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2012.12.002)).
- [16] J. Wang, Z. Fang, A. Gu, L. Xu and F. Liu, Effect of amino-functionalization of multi-walled carbon nanotubes on the dispersion with epoxy resin matrix, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **100**, 2006, pp. 97-104 (doi: [10.1002/app.22647](https://doi.org/10.1002/app.22647)).